
FRACTURED JUSTICE: THE RULE OF LAW AS RHETORIC AND REALITY IN CONTEMPORARY HUMAN RIGHTS DISCOURSE

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the intricate relationship between the Rule of Law and human rights, positing that the breakdown of one invariably precipitates the collapse of the other. Drawing on natural justice principles and social contract theory, it suggests individuals give up certain freedoms to the government in exchange for the protection of fundamental rights like life, liberty, and property. The discussion emphasises the importance of a government's ability to uphold these rights for its legitimacy, as highlighted by A.V. Dicey's characterisation of the Rule of Law as a safeguard against arbitrary actions. The paper also distinguishes between "thin" interpretations, focusing on legal processes, and "thick" ones, which incorporate broader notions of justice and human rights. It addresses challenges in applying the Rule of Law in authoritarian regimes where legal frameworks may justify human rights violations, exemplified by situations in Xinjiang and Russian-occupied Ukraine. Furthermore, it presents three strategies for enhancing human rights: Truth and Reconciliation Commissions (TRCs), a victim-centered justice approach, and strong civil society engagement. Over 20 post-conflict countries have effectively used TRCs to address past injustices. Ultimately, the Rule of Law is crucial for promoting justice and human rights globally.

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A. INTRODUCTION

“Where the rule of law fails, human rights fail along with it.” This statement poses a significant and perplexing challenge regarding the link between the rule of law and human rights. Natural justice is the foundation upon which a community is based, and citizens cede some of their rights to the state. The state is required to defend those rights in return.³ According to Grotius, the social drive to coexist peacefully and harmoniously with others is a fundamental human trait. Anything that was in line with men's and women's nature as social, logical creatures was good and just; anything that stood in the way of social peace was wrong and unjust.⁴ However, through cooperative efforts, society constructed a “social contract” to create a political unit and establish an organized society free from the risks and disadvantages inherent in the natural state of affairs. The basic rights of individuals, especially their rights to life, liberty, and property, were guaranteed by the contract. Consequently, should the government fail to safeguard these inherent rights, it would forfeit its legitimacy and authority.⁵ Understanding the origins of human rights and overcoming the problems associated with a consistent interpretation of these rights in modern times becomes critical.⁶ The Doctrine of the Rule of Law basically asserts that, under a democratic government, the law is supreme. At its core, the doctrine aims to limit the state's use of arbitrary authority and guarantee that the state strictly adheres to a set of fundamental processes and principles when creating, carrying out, and upholding laws. In the past 20 years, it has been a very potent concept for those opposing authoritarianism and totalitarianism, and many people believe it to be one of the primary tenets of a democratic government.⁷ A democratic society is guaranteed to be governed by the law, not the caprices of capricious officials working for an all-powerful state, according to this interpretation of the Doctrine.⁸ This Paper attempts to immerse readers in the complex conceptual underpinnings of the rule of law doctrine. By way of engaging discussions and a comprehensive examination of its fundamental concepts, readers will acquire an advanced understanding of its application. Furthermore, by delving into detailed case studies presented later, they will have the opportunity to critically assess the effectiveness of the doctrine's application in real-world contexts. This paper recognises

³ Jerome J. Shestack, *The Philosophic Foundation of Human Rights*, 20 HRQ 201, 206 (1998).

⁴ Jerome J. Shestack, *The Philosophic Foundation of Human Rights*, 20 HRQ 201, 207 (1998).

⁵ *Id.*

⁶ Robert P. George, *Natural Law*, 31 Harv. J.L. & Pub. Pol'y 171, 177 (2007).

⁷ G. O'Donnell, *Why the Rule of Law Matters*, 15 JOD 32, 35-36 (2004)

⁸ Smita & Udai Yashvir Sing, *Subversion Of The Doctrine Of Rule Of Law In The Current Indian Regime*, MANU (Mar. 10, 2025, 4:36 PM), <https://articles.manupatra.com/Article/ArticleDetails/Subversion-Of-The-Doctrine-Of-Rule-Of-Law-In-The-Current-Indian-Regime> .

the pervasive systemic violations occurring worldwide and puts forth specific restorative and strategic interventions designed to effectively address and mitigate the issue of human rights abuses.

B. THREADS OF JUSTICE: WEAVING SOCIETY WITH THE RULE OF LAW

Nowadays, the concept of the Rule of Law is practically universally accepted. Human rights activists view the Rule of Law as a vital instrument for preventing discrimination and the arbitrary use of force. Meanwhile, international financial organisations and legal development aid organisations vigorously promoted the Rule of Law, which was resurrected by libertarians like Hayek in the middle of the 20th century, as a necessary condition for the creation of effective market economies; on the other end of the political spectrum, even Marxists have begun to see the Rule of Law as an inalienable human right, whereas previously they saw it as only a formal super-structural safeguard for elite control.⁹ Alongside the idea that the state had a duty to provide substantive justice as well as to treat its citizens equally before the law, contemporary legal theorists contended that the old idea of the Rule of Law was no longer relevant to the modern world. An idea of law was created by several legal theories, including positivism, legal realism, and jurisprudence of interest. This freed the state from the inherent constraints imposed by a substantive concept of law. Any attempt to approximate the concept of the Rule of Law rests not only on the extension of rights in theory but also, perhaps more importantly, on how consistently the state upholds these rights. The conundrum that many democratic governments with significant levels of socioeconomic disparity face is this one. Governments do not feel compelled to uphold the duties associated with equal rights on an equal basis for all members of society. However, equal rights are acknowledged in the books as a symbolic gesture to gain cooperation.¹⁰ In modern democratic regimes, where high levels of inclusion are necessary for legitimacy and collaboration, rights are typically granted more liberally. However, even a democratic government does not require equal participation from all groups, so it has no motivation to always treat everyone equally under the law.

⁹ Rachel Kleinfeld (Truman National Security Project) et al Lisa Bhansali (World Bank), Christina Biebesheimer (World Bank), Wade Channell, Stephen Golub, David Mednicoff (University of Massachusetts, Amherst), Laure-Hélène Piron (Overseas Development Institute), Matthew Spence (Truman National Security Project), Matthew Stephenson (Harvard Law School), and Frank Upham (NYU School of Law), Promoting the Rule of Law Abroad: In Search of Knowledge 3-13 (Thomas Carothers, 2006).

¹⁰ Oscar Viera, Inequality and the Subversion of Rule of Law, 6 Intl J Hum Rts 27, 32-33 (2007).

Furthermore, the cost of collaboration will be disproportionate due to the unequal distribution of social, economic, and political resources held by various groups in society. This implies that the many clusters of advantages will influence the legislation and its execution.¹¹ British jurist A. V. Dicey conceptualized the phrase ‘Rule of law’ based on three clusters.¹² The first cluster pertains to the law's total supremacy. Therefore, the state's activities should be justified, and punishment should only be meted out for a clear violation of the law. The first strand likewise opposes the state’s broad discretionary power as it permits capricious actions by the state that violate the Rule of Law. The second cluster focuses only on equality before the law. Dicey argued that everyone should be treated equally under the nation’s common rules. This cluster demands that no man, regardless of position or status, be considered above the law, but it does not forbid unequal laws in and of themselves. The third cluster relates to the predominant legal spirit. It says that the general principles of the constitution emanate from the judges declaring the common law. The law is a result of individual rights. Dicey argued that common law ensures better governance than a constitutional code, i.e. a written constitution.

C. JUSTICE IN LAYERS: THICK AND THIN CONCEPTIONS OF THE RULE OF LAW IN HUMAN RIGHTS FRAMEWORKS

The rule of law is an essentially contested concept.¹³ The concept of the rule of law holds different meanings for different people and has been used to support various political agendas, including Lee Kuan Yew's soft authoritarianism, Rawlsian social welfare liberalism, Hayekian libertarianism, and Jiang Zemin's statist socialism.¹⁴ Philosophers with an analytical approach often outline the requirements that any legal system must fulfil to deserve the designation of “rule of law,” which establishes its essential elements. There is no single strategy that satisfies everyone, as each has its drawbacks and offers unique insights. Fortunately, there is a widely accepted conceptual and analytical framework that helps clarify some of the terms and debates surrounding the rule of law, despite the many arguments about its contentious nature. However, this framework does not address many critical related topics, which are often larger in scope. Formal conceptions of the rule of law, i.e. thin conception, refer to core elements that constitute the Doctrine. As encapsulated in the rhetorically potent

¹¹ *Id.*

¹² A.V. Dicey, Introduction to the study of the law of the constitution 172-173 (MacMillan & Co., 3rd ed. 1889).

¹³ Randall Peerenboom, Asian Discourses of Rule of Law 2-3 (UCLA School of Law, 1st ed. 2003).

¹⁴ *Id.*

but unduly simplistic ideas of a government of laws, the supremacy of the law, and equality of all before the law, the term “rule of law” in its most basic sense refers to a system in which the law can impose meaningful restraints on the state and individual members of the ruling elite. Inherently, formal conception of the doctrine, regardless of whether the legal system is a part of a capitalist, liberal, theocratic, or democratic society, a thin conception emphasizes the formal or instrumental aspects of the rule of law, those characteristics that any legal system is said to need in order to operate effectively as a system of laws.¹⁵ By defining the problem, distinguishing between thin and thick theories enables the rule of law to be used more successfully as a standard for assessing legal regimes. The good life and what is deemed right differ among liberals, socialists, communitarians, neo-authoritarians, soft-authoritarians, new conservatives, old conservatives, Buddhists, Daoist’s, neo-Confucians, and new Confucianists. As a result, they have different ideas about what the rule of law demands. Thick conceptions reduce the possibility of an overlapping consensus over the meaning of the rule of law by including specific ideas about the economy, political order, or human rights.¹⁶ Generally speaking, rights campaigners favour broad definitions of the rule of law over narrow ones. Thick theories enable reformers to address some contentious political topics under autocratic and oppressive regimes while ostensibly maintaining objectivity by presenting a complex examination of the rule of law. It is possible to avoid getting caught up in endless debates about the various political theories competing for the concept of justice by limiting the idea of the rule of law to the criteria of one specific theory. However, broader interpretations complicate the chances of reaching a common understanding of the rule of law, as they introduce specific ideas related to economics, political systems, or human rights. It is feasible to connect political and economic issues to law, legal institutions, and specific legal system ideas by articulating various dense concepts. Thick theories make it clearer what is at stake in many arguments by pointing out differences in opinions on a variety of topics. Furthermore, thick theories are typically preferred by activists and legal reformers in restrictive regimes because they enable them to address particular contentious political concerns.

¹⁵ Robert Summers, A Formal Theory of Rule of Law, vol. 6, no. 2 Ratio Juris 127, 133-134 (1993).

¹⁶ Jorgen Moller & Svend- Erik Skaaning, Systemazing Thick and Thin conceptions of the Rule of Law, vol. 33, no. 2 Justice Syst J. 136, 140-142 (2012).

D. FAULT LINES AND FOUNDATIONS: THE RULE OF LAW AS A MEDIATOR IN THE HUMAN RIGHTS DISCOURSE

“The desire for human rights is a powerful force, not easily comprehended by those of us who are free. Oppressed people will offer their lives to secure the rights that we take for granted.”¹⁷ However, the connection between the rule of law and human rights received very little attention from the human rights movement until recently.¹⁸ The preamble to the Universal Declaration of Human Rights mentions the rule of law in a typically covert manner that “human rights should be protected by the rule of law”.¹⁹ The early rights treaties, reports, resolutions, and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), along with the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR), fail to mention the rule of law. Presently, the rule of law concept can be inherently found in reports, charters, and regional workshop platforms. International accords have set consistent criteria, but the international community has had difficulty enforcing compliance under repressive regimes. World leaders must push for the acceptance and observance of international human rights safeguards when national laws deviate from these accepted standards. The preservation of rights is inextricably related to the rule of law. For many individuals worldwide, rights are only paper promises in the absence of the rule of law. Economic growth is crucial to reducing some of the worst human suffering, as one-fourth of the world's population lives below the international poverty line of \$581 per year per capita, 790 million people lack access to adequate nutrition, one billion people lack safe drinking water, two billion people lack proper sanitation, and 880 million people lack basic healthcare.²⁰ Specific, irrefutable conceptions arise due to the intersection of human rights with the doctrine of the rule of law. The Doctrine of the Rule of Law bridges the gap between human rights and fault lines concerning religious, economic and gender issues. Religious beliefs, traditional gender roles, conflicting views of freedom and autonomy, and fundamental beliefs regarding the relationship between individuals, the state, and society are just a few illustrations of significant moral commitments that have a significant role to play in most human rights issues.²¹ The freedom

¹⁷ Jimmy Carter, *The Rule of Law and the State of Human Rights*, 4 HARV. HUM. RTS. J 1, 6 (1991).

¹⁸ Henry J. Steiner & Philip Alston, *International Human Rights in Context: Law, Politics, Morals: Text and Materials* 1488 (2nd ed. 2000).

¹⁹ Universal Declaration of Human Rights, G.A. Res. 217A (III), U.N. GAOR, at 71, U.N. Doc A/810 (1948), available at <https://www.un.org/en/about-us/universal-declaration-of-human-rights>.

²⁰ Thomas W. Pogge, *Priorities of Global Justice* 8, (Thomas W. Pogge ed. 2001).

²¹ *Supra* at 7.

to practice one's religion and the freedom of others to practice their religion or to enjoy other freedoms are inherently at odds, and the liberal bias of the human rights movement has led to the inclusion of religious conflicts and tensions within liberalism. These factors are some of the reasons why religion in general continues to be a significant source of contention.²² A fault line that runs along the North-South, developed-developing country axis has been created by the growing wealth and poverty gaps within and between nations. Both in developed and emerging nations, increased wealth gaps have highlighted debates around positive and negative rights, leading to a reassessment of the international rights movement's emphasis on civil and political rights at the expense of economic rights.²³ Gender creates yet another division. Feminists argue that the human rights movement and international law are predominantly male-centric, often overlooking the concerns and interests of women; in addition, there are notable differences among feminists, which makes things much more complicated. Western rights advocates have been charged by women's rights advocates in non-Western nations with racism, paternalism, and ethnocentrism.²⁴ The rule of law provides several advantages that both liberals and communitarians will likely appreciate. For developing nations that are concerned with the right to development, the rule of law is essential for promoting growth. Additionally, feminists in the United States and around the world have effectively utilized the legal system to advocate for the enforcement of their rights, regardless of how those rights are defined. Therefore, focusing on the common ground established by the rule of law may serve as a means to rebuild goodwill and regain the momentum that has been lost in recent years amid the increasingly contentious debates that have fragmented the international rights community.

²² Bruce Ackerman, *Why Dialogue?*, 86 J. PHIL. 5, 16-17 (1989).

²³ Makau Wa Mutua, *Savages, Victims, and Saviors: The Metaphor of Human Rights*, 42 HARV. INT'L L.J. 201, 202 (2001).

²⁴ Radhika Coomaraswamy, *Identity Within: Cultural Relativism, Minority Rights and the Empowerment of Women*, 34 GEO. WASH. INT'L L. REV. 483, 485-486 (2002).

E. LEGAL FAÇADES AND HUMAN REALITIES: A CASE-BASED INQUIRY INTO THE CONTRADICTIONS OF THE RULE OF LAW

1. China's Legal Veil: The Uyghur Crisis and the Institutionalized Subversion of the Rule of Law

The repression of Uyghur Muslims in China's Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region (XUAR) is one of the worst human rights crises of the twenty-first century. This Turkic-speaking, mostly Muslim minority faces systematic discrimination and state-sponsored oppression. The Chinese government has launched a huge campaign of mass surveillance, arbitrary detention, forced labor, and cultural suppression.²⁵ These actions, which are mostly targeted against Uyghurs and other Muslim minorities, reflect both a profound disregard for international human rights norms and a calculated dismantling of the rule of law. Over one million Uyghurs have been detained in so-called “vocational education and training centres,” which are widely recognised as internment camps.²⁶ Individuals have been arrested for benign acts such as praying, growing beards, wearing headscarves, or having contacts abroad. These mass detentions violate the fundamental right to liberty and security of person, as protected under Article 3 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) and Article 9 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR). The detentions are arbitrary and illegal under international law since the detainees are frequently denied access to family, legal counsel, and trials. Eyewitness accounts from survivors reveal shocking abuses inside the camps, including torture, beatings, rape, solitary confinement, and forced sterilisation. These practices violate Article 5 of the UDHR and China's own commitments under the UN Convention Against Torture, which it ratified. Religious freedom, enshrined under Article 18 of the UDHR, is routinely denied to Uyghurs. Mosques have been demolished, Qurans banned, and Islamic customs suppressed.²⁷ People are coerced into eating pork and drinking

²⁵ U.N. Office of the U.N. High Commissioner for Human Rights., OHCHR Assessment of Human Rights Concerns in the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region, People's Republic of China, ¶ 8 (Aug. 31, 2022), <https://www.ohchr.org/sites/default/files/documents/countries/2022-08-31/22-08-31-final-assesment.pdf>.

²⁶ Human Rights Watch, “Break Their Lineage, Break Their Roots”: China's Crimes Against Humanity Targeting Uyghurs and Other Turkic Muslims, HUMAN RIGHTS WATCH (Apr. 19, 2021), <https://www.hrw.org/report/2021/04/19/break-their-lineage-break-their-roots/chinas-crimes-against-humanity-targeting>.

²⁷ Kaamil Ahmed, Elderly Uyghur Women Imprisoned in China for Decades-Old Religious 'Crimes', Leaked Files Reveal, THE GUARDIAN (Feb. 1, 2024), <https://www.theguardian.com/global-development/2024/feb/01/elderly-uyghur-women-imprisoned-in-china-for-decades-old-religious-crimes-leaked-files-reveal>.

alcohol, and practising Islam is labelled “extremism.” The state’s objective appears to be the total erasure of Uyghur religious and cultural identity.

China has also implemented policies aimed at forced cultural assimilation. The Uyghur language is banned in schools, and Mandarin is enforced as the primary language of instruction.²⁸ Festivals, music, and cultural customs are prohibited. Children are taken to state-run boarding schools to be brought up as devoted Communist Party members when families are forcibly split apart. These actions violate Article 27 of the ICCPR, which protects minority cultural and linguistic rights. Additionally, credible reports of forced labor in factories, often linked to global supply chains, violate the right to free choice of employment under Article 23 of the UDHR and International Labor Organisation (ILO) conventions.²⁹ Perhaps most alarming is the evidence of reproductive coercion. Uyghur women have been subjected to forced sterilisations, abortions, and birth control measures designed to suppress population growth.³⁰ These practices may amount to genocide under Article II of the Genocide Convention, particularly the intent “to prevent births within the group.”³¹ Combined with mass internment and cultural destruction, these policies reflect a coordinated attempt to eliminate the Uyghur identity itself.

The Chinese government has eroded the rule of law in Xinjiang as the internment system operates outside judicial oversight, with no access to courts or legal remedies. China’s counter terrorism and de-extremification laws are vaguely worded and arbitrarily applied, giving the police unchecked power. Citizens can be labelled threats without evidence or a trial. The surveillance regime in Xinjiang is among the most invasive in the world, with facial recognition, biometric data collection, and AI-driven profiling used to monitor daily life. This violates the presumption of innocence, the right to privacy, and all principles of legal proportionality.

²⁸ Nathan Ruser, Dr James Leibold, Kelsey Munro, Tila Hoja, Cultural Erasure: Tracing the Destruction of Uyghur and Islamic Spaces in Xinjiang, AUSTRALIAN STRATEGIC POLICY INSTITUTE (Sept. 24, 2020) <https://www.aspi.org.au/report/cultural-erasure>.

²⁹ Amy K. Lehr, Coercive Labor in the Cotton Harvest in the Xinjiang Uyghur Autonomous Region, 56 CPCS 1, (2022), <https://online.ucpress.edu/cpcs/article/56/2/1/196124/Coercive-Labor-in-the-Cotton-Harvest-in-the>.

³⁰ Magnus Fiskesjö, Bulldozing Culture: China’s Systematic Destruction of Uyghur Heritage Reveals Genocidal Intent, Xinjiang Documentation Project, CULTURAL PROPERTY NEWS (June 23, 2021), <https://culturalpropertynews.org/bulldozing-culture-chinas-systematic-destruction-of-uyghur-heritage-reveals-genocidal-intent/>

³¹ U.S. Dep’t of Labor, Against Their Will: The Situation in Xinjiang, DEPARTMENT OF LABOUR, <https://www.dol.gov/agencies/ilab/against-their-will-the-situation-in-xinjiang>.

Judicial institutions in Xinjiang serve the interests of the Communist Party, not the constitution or the people. Courts lack independence, and lawyers who attempt to challenge state narratives are arrested or disbarred. The international human rights enforcers are regularly denied entry to the region, and dissent of any form is censored by the state media in China. The lack of legal transparency, equitable trials, and judicial oversight indicates an entire collapse of the rule of law. Not only does the government abuse rights, but it also cuts off any means for accountability or justice. Despite growing international condemnation, including a 2022 UN report affirming credible evidence of crimes against humanity, global action has been limited. Several governments, including the United States, Canada, and the United Kingdom, have recognised China's actions as genocide. However, China's political and economic sway in organisations such as the ICC and the UN makes effective legal accountability impossible. Hence Uyghur people are left in a legal limbo, their identity under jeopardy, and their fundamental rights suspended.

In conclusion, the treatment of Uyghur Muslims in China is not just a human rights issue, it is a direct assault on the very principles of law, justice, and international order. China has established a parallel system of government in Xinjiang that disregards both national legal standards and international human rights commitments using ambiguous legislation, unbridled executive power, and the repression of opposition. The failure to uphold the rule of law in this case allows the state to commit abuses with impunity, leaving millions without protection or recourse. The international community must confront this crisis with urgency, not only to protect the Uyghur people but to defend the integrity of the global human rights framework itself.

2. Erasing Identity, Rewriting Law: The Legal Assault on Ukrainian Civilians and Sovereignty

The Russia-Ukraine war, which escalated dramatically with Russia's full-scale invasion in February 2022, has been marked by serious human rights violations and a systematic subversion of the rule of law. The conflict has not only caused widespread human suffering but has also highlighted how legal systems can be manipulated or destroyed in times of war, particularly in areas under foreign occupation. At the heart of the rule of law is the idea that all individuals and institutions are subject to and accountable under the law. However, this basic idea has been eroded in Russian-occupied countries. By implementing Russian laws

and restricting Ukrainian identity, Russian authorities have supplanted Ukrainian legal systems with their own.³² These areas subject Ukrainian nationals to forced legal assimilation, arbitrary incarceration, and sham trials without due process or legal representation. Civilians have frequently been jailed for merely opposing occupation or expressing support for Ukraine, and trials have been held behind closed doors without any fairness or transparency.³³

The prosecution of Ukrainian civilians and POWs in Russian-occupied territories is among the most concerning instances. People are frequently charged with being “terrorists” or “Nazi collaborators,” prosecuted without due process, and given severe punishments, such as life in jail.³⁴ This violates both international human rights law and the Geneva Conventions, which protect the rights of civilians and prisoners of war in conflict zones. The use of courts as tools of oppression instead of justice is a direct subversion of the rule of law. Another legal breach is when Ukrainian civilians in occupied territories are forcibly imposed Russian citizenship. Civilians are often told they will lose access to basic rights such as healthcare, pensions, and employment unless they accept Russian passports. Individual autonomy and free choice, which are fundamental to both international human rights legislation and the rule of law, are violated by this compulsion. It also establishes a risky precedent for using legal systems to legitimise occupation and annexation.

In addition, it is a violation of international criminal law and human rights when Ukrainian children are deported to Russia or territories under Russian control, frequently with their Ukrainian identity erased and adopted into Russian households.³⁵ The legal system safeguarding children's rights in armed situations is being attacked by these acts, including the ban on forced relocation and cultural erasure. Russia's disregard for the rule of law, even within its own borders, is shown by the suppression of dissent over the conflict. The Russian government has misused ambiguous laws that forbid “disinformation” against Journalists,

³² Amnesty Int'l, Russia/Ukraine: A Decade of Suppressing Non-Russian Identities in Occupied Crimea AMESTY INTRNATIONAL, (Mar. 18, 2024), <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2024/03/russia-ukraine-a-decade-of-suppressing-non-russian-identities-in-occupied-crimea/>

³³ Fabian Burkhardt, The Four Modi of Russia's Forced Naturalization of Ukrainians, 3 UKRAINE ANALYTICAL DIGEST 13 (2023), https://www.ssoar.info/ssoar/bitstream/handle/document/91241/ssoar-ukrainad-2023-3-burkhardt-The_Four_Modis_of_Russias.pdf.

³⁴ *Id.*

³⁵ European Parliamentary Research Service, Russia's War on Ukraine: Forcibly Displaced Ukrainian Children, EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT (Feb. 11, 2025), [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI\(2023\)747093](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/thinktank/en/document/EPRS_BRI(2023)747093).

activists, and citizens who oppose the invasion.³⁶ This crackdown on free speech and peaceful protest further shows how war has become an excuse for eroding democratic norms and silencing opposition.

In conclusion, in addition to causing physical devastation, the conflict between Russia and Ukraine has also led to the collapse of the legitimate government. The persecution of civilians demonstrates a serious subversion of the rule of law, the denial of due process, and the manipulation of judicial systems to further military and political objectives. Rebuilding the post-war world and guaranteeing long-term peace and stability will need the restoration of justice, accountability, and legal order.

3. Fragmented Sovereignty: Legal Inequality and the Collapse of Accountability in the Israel-Palestine Conflict

The Israel–Palestine conflict involves decades of violence and occupation, with serious concerns over human rights abuses and erosion of the rule of law. In Gaza, over 2 million Palestinians live under a land, sea, and air blockade since 2007. This blockade, amounting to collective punishment, severely limits access to food, water, electricity, and medical care, violating international humanitarian law and the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR).³⁷

Since October 2023, escalating military operations have led to large-scale civilian casualties. Over 30,000 Palestinians, including women and children, have been killed, and essential civilian infrastructure including hospitals, schools and refugee camps has been destroyed.³⁸ These attacks violate international humanitarian law, especially the principles of distinction, proportionality, and precaution under the Geneva Conventions. Rights groups and UN agencies have raised allegations of war crimes due to indiscriminate attacks and failure to protect civilians.

³⁶ Andrés Koltay, Russian Bans on 'Fake News' About the War in Ukraine: Conditional Truth and Unconditional Loyalty, 10 J. Int'l Media & Ent. L. 1 (2024), <https://www.swlaw.edu/sites/default/files/2024-01/JIMEL%2010.1%20Koltay231215.pdf>.

³⁷ Human Rights Watch, Israel/Palestine: An Abyss of Human Suffering in Gaza, HUMAN RIGHTS WATCH (Jan. 16, 2025), <https://www.hrw.org/news/2025/01/16/israel/palestine-abyss-human-suffering-gaza>.

³⁸ Amnesty International, Human Rights in Israel and the Occupied Palestinian Territory, AMNESTY INTERNATIONAL <https://www.amnesty.org/en/location/middle-east-and-north-africa/middle-east/israel-and-the-occupied-palestinian-territory/report-israel-and-the-occupied-palestinian-territory/>.

In the West Bank, Palestinians face a discriminatory and biased dual legal system. Israeli settlers are governed by Israeli civil law, while Palestinians are subject to Israeli military law. This violates the principle of legal equality under Article 26 of the ICCPR. Due process and international juvenile justice standards are frequently violated by arbitrary arrests, administrative detentions without trial, and the military prosecution of minors.

Further restrictions on freedom of movement, expression, and assembly are imposed through checkpoints, curfews, and permit systems. The demolition of Palestinian homes and expansion of illegal Israeli settlements, in violation of Article 49 of the Fourth Geneva Convention, erode the Palestinian right to self-determination under international law. Palestinian armed groups, including Hamas, have also committed violations by launching rockets into civilian areas of Israel.³⁹ Since these attack fails to distinguish between military and civilian targets, breaches international humanitarian law. However, the imbalance in military power and destruction, especially in Gaza, highlights how systemic occupation and blockade fuel the cycle of violence.

The lack of accountability undermines the rule of law. Investigations have stagnated in spite of repeated requests from the ICC and UN agencies.⁴⁰ Israel rejects the International Criminal Court's authority over Palestine, and frequently vetoes UN Security Council initiatives. This legal immobility makes it possible for abuses to go unpunished, which makes it harder to enforce human rights standards globally.

In conclusion, the Israel–Palestine conflict reflects entrenched human rights violations, legal discrimination, and failure of international accountability. Without equal application of law and genuine efforts for justice, the situation will remain a humanitarian crisis and a challenge to the global rule of law.

³⁹ Amnesty International, Israel: Palestinian Armed Groups Must Be Held Accountable for Deliberate Civilian Killings, Abductions and Indiscriminate Attacks, AMESTY INTERNATIONAL (Oct. 10, 2023), <https://www.amnesty.org/en/latest/news/2023/10/israel-palestinian-armed-groups-must-be-held-accountable-for-deliberate-civilian-killings-abductions-and-indiscriminate-attacks/>.

⁴⁰ Office of the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, UN Report Calls for Accountability, Justice for Violations by All Parties, OHCHR (Feb. 23, 2024), <https://www.ohchr.org/en/press-releases/2024/02/un-report-calls-accountability-justice-violations-all-parties-opt-and-israel>

4. Authoritarianism and Accountability: North Korea's Defiance of International Law

North Korea, officially the Democratic People's Republic of Korea (DPRK), is widely considered one of the most authoritarian and opaque regimes in the world. Since 1948, the country has been ruled by the Kim dynasty, currently under Kim Jong-un, where power is centralised in a single person and enforced through fear, propaganda, and repression. The regime functions without separation of powers; the executive dominates the judiciary and legislature, and there is no independent media or civil society.⁴¹ As a result, there is a total absence of the rule of law. Impartial courts or accountable institutions do not protect citizens. Since the ruling Workers' Party has direct influence over the judiciary, legislation is made to further the regime's goals rather than justice or individual rights. Detainees frequently face torture, arbitrary arrests, and secret trials without access to counsel or the presumption of innocence.

Political prison camps, known as kwanliso, are one of the most egregious symbols of North Korea's human rights violations. These camps hold up to 120,000 people in conditions that amount to crimes against humanity. Entire families are often imprisoned under the principle of "guilt by association", a direct violation of international law which upholds individual criminal responsibility.⁴² Inmates suffer forced labour, starvation, physical abuse, sexual violence, and summary executions. Article 5 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), which prohibits torture and cruel treatment, is routinely violated. The right to a fair and public trial (Article 10, UDHR and Article 14, ICCPR) is non-existent. People are often detained for vague "anti-state" acts, without ever being charged or tried.

Basic civil and political rights are severely restricted. Freedom of speech, religion, movement, and assembly, protected under Articles 18, 19, and 20 of the UDHR, is entirely suppressed. Criticising the regime or consuming foreign media is treated as treason. Underground Christians are subjected to severe persecution, and religious activities are prohibited unless they support state ideology.⁴³ There is a lot of surveillance; neighbours, coworkers, and even family members are enlisted as informants, which causes self-censorship and generalised fear.

⁴¹ Human Rights Watch, World Report 2023: North Korea, HUMAN RIGHTS WATCH <https://www.hrw.org/world-report/2023/country-chapters/north-korea>.

⁴² U.N. Human Rights Council, Report of the Commission of Inquiry on Human Rights in the Democratic People's Republic of Korea, U.N. Doc. A/HRC/25/63 (Feb. 7, 2014).

⁴³ *Id.*

People are kept isolated from the outside world by the regime's control over communication and information, as well as internet isolation.

The regime also violates international refugee law. Defectors who manage to escape into neighbouring countries, especially China, are often forcibly returned. Upon repatriation, they are imprisoned, tortured, or executed, violating the principle of non-refoulement under customary international law. Women and children, particularly along the China-North Korea border, are vulnerable to trafficking, forced marriages, and sexual slavery.⁴⁴ Gender-based violence is rampant, and women in detention often face forced abortions and sexual abuse, with no access to legal redress. Additionally, widespread food insecurity, lack of medical care, and malnutrition violate the right to an adequate standard of living.

Despite North Korea being a signatory to several international treaties, including the ICCPR and the Convention on the Rights of the Child, it routinely disregards its obligations. The UN Commission of Inquiry's 2014 report concluded that the DPRK commits "systematic, widespread and gross human rights violations" that may constitute crimes against humanity. International attempts to hold the regime responsible, however, have encountered difficulties. North Korea denies the International Criminal Court's jurisdiction and is not a signatory to the Rome Statute. Furthermore, measures that would have opened the door for legal accountability have been blocked by China and Russia, permanent members of the UN Security Council, using their veto rights.

In conclusion, North Korea represents one of the clearest examples of a total collapse of the rule of law and institutionalized human rights abuse in the modern world. The regime uses its legal system not to uphold justice, but to maintain control through fear and brutality. International legal norms, human rights conventions, and the rule of law are systematically ignored. For the millions of North Koreans who continue to perish in a system that renders their existence illegal, international enforcement tools may never be put in place due to geopolitics and the constant impasse. Now the international community must continue to document violations, assist those who have defected, and start to promote mechanisms that can finally operate to deliver justice and accountability to the victim.

⁴⁴ Human Rights Watch, China Forcibly Returns 60 Refugees to North Korea, HUMAN RIGHTS WATCH (May 8, 2024), <https://www.hrw.org/news/2024/05/08/china-forcibly-returns-60-refugees-north-korea>.

5. Institutional Failure and the Death of George Floyd: A Human Rights Perspective

The death of George Floyd on May 25, 2020, exposed critical violations of human rights and a breakdown in the rule of law in the United States. Floyd, a 46-year-old African American man, was killed when Minneapolis police officer Derek Chauvin knelt on his neck for 9 minutes and 29 seconds during an arrest, despite Floyd being handcuffed, subdued, and repeatedly stating, "I can't breathe." This excessive use of force violated Article 3 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), which guarantees the right to life, and Article 5, which prohibits cruel and inhuman treatment.⁴⁵

Floyd's death also reflected systemic racial discrimination,⁴⁶ breaching Article 7 of the UDHR, which guarantees equality before the law. Article 8 guarantees access to an efficient judicial remedy but was hampered by the first attempt to characterise Floyd's death as a medical occurrence and the postponement of the officers' prosecution.⁴⁷ In this case, law enforcement authorities behaved without consequence and were initially exempt from accountability, exposing a significant breakdown of the rule of law. Although Chauvin was eventually convicted and sentenced to over 22 years, and the other officers received prison terms for civil rights violations, these outcomes were seen as rare exceptions.⁴⁸ The failure to pass the George Floyd Justice in Policing Act demonstrated the political resistance to meaningful reform.⁴⁹ Floyd's case generated global protests and a UN denunciation of institutional racism, calling for a drastic need for structural reform.⁵⁰ It came to symbolize uneven application of the law, institutional failures, and intrinsic biases threatening justice

⁴⁵ Jennifer Venis, George Floyd Killing: Discriminatory, Disproportionate Use of Force by Police Undermines Rule of Law, INTERNATIONAL BAR ASSOCIATION (June 9, 2020), <https://www.ibanet.org/article/69752576-cd78-48ed-8f0f-ae50433fb950> .

⁴⁶ Shahrzad Toosi, Recognizing Racism in George Floyd's Death, 75 ANALYSES OF SOC. ISSUES & PUB. POL'Y 1 (2021), <https://spssi.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/asap.12282>

⁴⁷ The Robina Inst. of Crim. L. & Crim. Just., The George Floyd Homicide Prosecutions, ROBINA INSTITUTE, (Jan. 11, 2020), <https://robinainstitute.umn.edu/articles/george-floyd-homicide-prosecutions>.

⁴⁸ E. Tendayi Achiume, George Floyd at the UN: Whiteness, International Law, and Police Violence, 7 U.C. IRVINE J. INT'L, TRANSNAT'L, & COMP. L. 91 (2021), <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/1jm5k9mc> .

⁴⁹ Legal Defence Fund, LDF Issues Statement on the Failure to Advance the George Floyd Justice in Policing Act of 2021, NAACP LEGAL DEFENCE FUND (Sept. 22, 2021), <https://www.naacpldf.org/press-release/ldf-issues-statement-on-the-failure-to-advance-the-george-floyd-justice-in-policing-act-of-2021/>.

⁵⁰ William Jaffe, United States: UN Human Rights Mechanism Finds Excessive Force, Racism in Policing, PHYSICIANS FOR HUMAN RIGHTS (Oct. 28, 2022), <https://phr.org/our-work/resources/emler-mechanism-finds-excessive-force-racism-in-policing/> .

and human rights. The challenge remains to build a legal system that is fair, accountable, and respects the rights of all individuals, regardless of race or status

F. BRIDGING THE DIVIDE: RESTORATIVE MEASURES FOR RECLAIMING THE RULE OF LAW IN RIGHTS-VIOLATING REGIMES

After conducting an in-depth analysis of the legal doctrine and examining real-life case studies, it becomes increasingly evident to devise and implement targeted measures to effectively safeguard human rights and uphold the rule of law. It is essential to create a robust framework that not only prevents violations but also fosters a climate of respect and protection for all individuals.

1. Truth and Reconciliation Commissions (TRCs)

The most important human rights tools for post-conflict reconstruction lie in the application of Truth and Reconciliation Commissions (TRCs). TRCs are based somewhat on the ideas of restorative justice—they examine past wrong-doings and do their best to heal some of society's wounds relating to violence through personal testimony to martyrdom and witnessing.⁵¹ Within this framework, social workers play a crucial yet often overlooked role in enhancing the well-being of communities engaged in the healing process facilitated by TRCs. Their expertise is vital in promoting restorative practices and addressing the psychosocial needs of affected populations. Established for the first time in South Africa after the end of the apartheid regime to restore the rights of the citizens which were earlier violated. The TRC presented a 'working relationship' between truth and justice.⁵² Since 1973, "truth commissions" have emerged as a leading mechanism for addressing past injustices and fostering peace in post-conflict societies; during the past decades, more than 20 of these commissions have been established across the globe.⁵³ Notably, the period between 1974 and 1994 witnessed a remarkable proliferation of these bodies, with a total of 15 commissions formed during these two decades alone. These truth commissions have various functions, with the main ones being to establish the truth regarding previous human rights abuses, to give victims a forum to tell their stories, and to facilitate healing in communities divided by violence and oppression. In the years 1992 and 1993, truth commissions were established in

⁵¹ Elizabeth Stanley, Evaluating the Truth and Reconciliation Commission, 39 CUP 525, 526-527 (2001).

⁵² *Id.*

⁵³ Kevin Avruch & Beatriz Vejarano, Truth and Reconciliation Commissions: A Review Essay and Annotated Bibliography, 4.2 OJPCR 37, 37- 38 (2002)

El Salvador with the financial and technical support of the UN. To redress the past injustices, the non-governmental organizations also created commissions of the same nature in 1976 in Paraguay and in 1993 in Rwanda. The African National Congress (ANC) facilitated two investigative commissions in South Africa during 1992 and 1993, aimed at scrutinising the organisation's conduct amid the anti-Apartheid movement. In the wake of the dismantling of Apartheid, the newly formed South African parliament established the South African Commission of Truth and Reconciliation in 1995, culminating in the publication of its comprehensive report in October 1998.⁵⁴ International organizations have formed certain commissions which include about the UN, and yet many are established by national governments themselves. This phenomenon depicts the complex interrelationship of domestic political will and international norms about accountability and justice.

2. From Harm to Healing: A Victim-Centered Approach to Post-Violation Redress

This is a victim-centric approach based on the principles of retributive and restorative justice. Retributive justice is a conceptual framework focused on penalising offenders to reaffirm societal norms and values. The major purpose of criminal law is to ensure that all offenders are punished in accordance with the moral order of society.⁵⁵ Punishment has two existences in opposite orientations: one is backed by indignation from the public for a violation of laws, norms, and moral codes.⁵⁶ This framework underscores the connection between punishment, morality, and community values within the larger discussion on justice and accountability. Restorative justice employs a bilateral process that brings together all stakeholders affected by an offense to collaboratively determine the most effective means of addressing the harm caused.⁵⁷ Central to restorative justice is the goal of restoring all parties involved, the offender, the victim, and the community, often including supporters from both sides as well as community members without affiliations. This approach condemns the harmful act while refraining from demonizing the individual perpetrator, thus facilitating the offender's reintegration as a law-abiding member of society. For victims, restorative justice seeks not only material restitution but also psychological healing, endeavouring to restore their sense of

⁵⁴ *Id.*

⁵⁵ Carlsmith & Darley, Psychological aspects of retributive justice, 40 AESP. 193, 199-200 (2008).

⁵⁶ Carlsmith, The roles of retribution and utility in determining punishment, 42 J. Exp. Soc. Psychol. 437, 444-445 (2006).

⁵⁷ Dena M. Gromet et al. Tyler G. Okimoto, Michael Wenzel & John M. Darley, A Victim-Centered Approach to Justice? Victim Satisfaction Effects on Third-Party Punishments, 36 Law Hum. Behav. 375, 375-376 (2012).

well-being to the state it was in prior to the offense.⁵⁸ As it was the initial organization to have the law respect victims' rights to pursue remedies, the International Criminal Court (ICC) is an important evolution of the protection of victims' rights in international criminal justice. Nevertheless, considerable uncertainty remains as to how the ICC and broader framework of international criminal justice facilitate victim compensation.⁵⁹ Furthermore, this is alongside a complementary source of advocacy and support as regards victims' rights, that coming from a global rights movement. While the rise of this new paradigm has brought a heightened focus on victims' rights and needs, it has not brought such a sophisticated international attention toward victims themselves.⁶⁰ A seminal moment in this regard occurred in 1985, when the United Nations General Assembly endorsed the inaugural global report on crime victims. The principles articulated in the Declaration of Basic Principles of Justice for Victims of Crime and Abuse of Power underscore that “victims are entitled to prompt redress and access to the mechanisms of justice,” thereby reinforcing the imperative for justice systems to accommodate and address the needs of this often-marginalised population. Presently, the ICC has issued reparations concerning the ongoing situation in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, focusing on collective and individual reparations to bridge the gap between the existing human rights and the rule of law.

3. An Examination of Civil Society’s Role in Bridging Human Rights and the Rule of Law

Post-conflict reconstruction processes more and more focus on the creation of robust institutions to ensure the rule of law. Scholars and practitioners concur that addressing past injustices and seeking accountability for serious human rights abuses committed during wars is essential to ensuring a stable and secure environment. The mechanisms employed to confront past human rights abuses in post-conflict contexts, including truth commissions, reparations frameworks, and judicial tribunals, are collectively categorised under the umbrella of transitional justice.⁶¹ These initiatives are imperative not only to acknowledge the experiences of the victims, but also to instil healing for society and preventing violence in the future. The efforts to rebuild following a war typically revolve around building institutions

⁵⁸ *Id.*

⁵⁹ Nao Shimoyachi, *Between Accountability and Reconciliation: The Making of “The Victim-Centered Approach” at the International Criminal Court*, 4 GSQ 1, 2 (2024).

⁶⁰ Nao Shimoyachi, *Between Accountability and Reconciliation: The Making of “The Victim-Centered Approach” at the International Criminal Court*, 4 GSQ 1, 3 (2024).

⁶¹ Eric Brahm, *Transitional Justice, Civil Society, and the Development of the Rule of Law in Post-Conflict Societies*, Vol. 9 Iss. 4 IJNL., 1, 1-2 (2007).

that ensure adherence to the rule of law, and this is an excellent tactic.⁶² Inescapably, civil society groups have played an important role in the development and promotion of transitional justice efforts worldwide. Yet it is worrying that civil society remains weak, fragmented, and often lacks autonomy to effect change in most post-conflict nations. Civil society is crucial in seeking justice for historical human rights abuses in post-conflict situations. The capacity of non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to rehabilitate and operate again during periods of turbulence is critical, since these organisations may use their power to pressure interim governments to conduct comprehensive inquiries into previous wrongdoings. Additionally, the formation of victim groups in the wake of conflict, especially in areas where they were previously absent, marks a significant change. These groups are often motivated by a deep desire for justice and accountability, and their efforts can significantly contribute to achieving legal and social remedies in various cases. When governments neglect their duty to address human rights violations, civil society organisations frequently assume the responsibility of conducting investigations akin to those of truth commissions. In 1979, the São Paulo Archbishop and the World Council of Churches initiated a clandestine inquiry into the human rights violations of the military government. Legal experts affiliated with the Catholic Church systematically reviewed documents enabling them to evaluate more than 700 cases presented before military tribunals.⁶³ Global civil society can significantly contribute to fundraising initiatives, offering legitimacy and moral support, while also sharing crucial knowledge and insights gained from other countries' experiences with transitional justice. Because of their widespread presence, groups like Human Rights Watch and Amnesty International are able to effectively track and disseminate information regarding initiatives meant to advance accountability.⁶⁴ Their extensive advocacy and communication programs promote participation on a national and worldwide level and improve knowledge of transitional justice systems.

G. CONCLUSION

Human rights and the Rule of Law are inextricably linked; as one deteriorates, the other unavoidably suffers. Natural justice and the social compact idea, which holds that people give up some liberties in order to protect their essential rights most notably, life, liberty, and

⁶² *Id.*

⁶³ Eric Brahm, *Transitional Justice, Civil Society, and the Development of the Rule of Law in Post-Conflict Societies*, Vol. 9 Iss. 4 IJNL., 1, 4-5 (2007).

⁶⁴ *Id.*

property—are the foundations of this relationship. A government is valid if it can uphold basic rights, and the Rule of Law is a necessary protection from the unreasonable use of government powers. The perspectives articulated by Grotius and A.V. Dicey establish that the Rule of Law has to be more than ensuring equitable legal processes in order to protect human rights and the quest for justice. The “thin” and “thick” lenses that can be used to analyze this dual role may differ depending on the cultural and ideological setting. The difficulties faced by authoritarian governments, which are distinguished by their manipulation of the legal system to excuse abuses of human rights, emphasize the necessity of a strong Rule of Law. To address these challenges effectively, strategies such as Truth and Reconciliation Commissions (TRCs), victim-centred justice frameworks, and the proactive engagement of civil society are essential for advancing human rights. The success of TRCs in post-conflict environments illustrates their potential for rectifying historical injustices, while victim-centred justice harmonizes retributive and restorative principles. Moreover, the active participation of civil society in advocating for legal reforms and demanding governmental accountability remains critical. Enhancing the Rule of Law worldwide is essential for advancing justice and safeguarding human rights. The pledge ensures that every person's inherent dignity is respected and guarded in every culture, leading to a more equitable and fairer society.

